

Application of Two Dip Two Pad Dyeing of Cotton Fabric with Reactive Dyes and Find Out the Suitable Condition Based on L9 Control- Level Factors Design

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

Dyeing of cotton fabrics with Reactive Red 2 using padding method (two dip two pad) was done; the fixation of dyeing fabric had been done using either thermo fixation technique. Different parameters such as dyeing time, dye concentration, drying temperature and PH were used. The controllable factors such as dyeing time, dye concentration, drying temperature and PH have been used as input variables and K/S value of the fabric (after dyeing and after soaping) to find out fixation percentage i.e. as response variable for the construction of Taguchi model and Single Factor model. An L₉ orthogonal array design has been chosen and conducted 9 experiments for each experiment. The optimal parameters in the dyeing process of Reactive Red 2 have been identified as PH 10, dye concentration 5 g/L, drying time 3 min and drying temperature 70 °C. From Pareto Chart analysis we found the optimizing sequences are PH (A) (10) > Dyeing concentration (C) (5 gm/L) > Drying Temperature (B) (70°C) > Drying Time (D) (3 minute) for Reactive Red 2. ANOVA implies that PH & Drying time is the most significant factor of Reactive Red 2. The Taguchi model derived in this research has been verified via confirmation experiment and unseen experimental data. In addition, the confirmation experimental S/N ratio 38.7 under optimal conditions is found to be good agreement with the predicted S/N ratio 38.45 for Reactive Red 2.

Keywords: DIP PAD DYEING, COTTON FABRIC, REACTIVE DYE, SINGLE FACTOR METHOD, TAGHUCHI METHOD AND S/N RATIO.

1. Introduction

Cotton is the most important natural textile fiber, as well as cellulosic textile fibre in the world, used to produce apparel, home furnishings, and industrial products. Worldwide about 40% of the fiber consumed in 2004 was cotton(1). Cotton is grown mostly for fiber but it is also a food (cotton seed)—the major end uses for cottons seeds are vegetable oil for human consumption; whole seed,

meal, and hulls for animal feed; and linters for batting and chemical cellulose(2). Each one of the commercially important species contain many different varieties developed through breeding programs to produce cottons with continually improving properties (e.g., faster maturing, increased yields, and improved insect and disease resistance) and fibers with greater length, strength, and uniformity.

The fiber is long and fine with a staple length usually greater than 1 (35mm) and a micronaire, value of below 4.0. If grown in the United States lint fibres are usually 33-36 mm (1.83 to 1.5 inch) long(3). Commonly known as extra-long staple (ELS), it supplies about 8% of the current world production of cotton fiber. This group includes the commercial varieties of Egyptian, American–Egyptian, and Sea Island cottons. Egypt and Sudan are the primary producers of ELS cottons in the world today(4). Pima, which is also ELS cotton, is a complex cross of Egyptian and American Upland strains and is grown in the western United States (mainly California with some in Arizona, southwestern Texas, and New Mexico), as well as in South America(5). Pima has many of the characteristics of the better Egyptian cottons. Raw cotton fiber, after ginning and mechanical cleaning, is approximately 95% cellulose. The structure of cotton cellulose, a linear polymer of β -D- glucopyranose. The non-cellulosic constituents of the fiber are located principally in the cuticle, in the primary cell wall, and in the lumen. Cotton fibers that have a high ratio of surface area linear density generally exhibit a relatively higher non-cellulosic content(6). The non-cellulosic constituents include proteins, amino acids, other nitrogen -containing compounds, wax, pectic substances, organic acids, sugars, inorganic salts, and a very small amount of pigments. Variations in these constituents arise due to differences in fiber maturity, variety of cotton and environmental conditions (soil, climate, farming practices, etc). After treatments to remove the naturally occurring non cellulosic materials, the cellulose content of the fiber is over 99%(7). The cotton fiber is predominantly cellulose and its chemical reactivity is the same as that of the cellulose polymer, a β -1,4-linked glucan. The chemical structure shows that the 2-OH, 3-OH, and 6-OH sites are potentially available for the same chemical reactions that occur with alcohols(8). If the glucan were water soluble, the primary 6-OH, for steric reasons, would be the most available hydroxyl for the reaction. However, as discussed earlier, the chains of cellulose molecules associate with each other by forming intermolecular hydrogen bonds and hydrophobic bonds. These coalesce to form microfibrils that are organized into macrofibrils(9). The macrofibrils are organized into fibers which are shown below in Fig 1.

Figure 1: Ordinary reactions of chemical agents with cellulose are almost exclusively with the 2,3 and 6 hydroxyl groups that are not involved in formation of the linear polymer consisting of D-anhydroglucose units joined via β -1,4-linkag

2. Materials and methods

100% Cotton plain woven fabric (160 GSM) was used for this experiment. The woven fabrics were collected from the H.H Textile mills Ltd, Borpa, Rupgong, Narayangong. Reactive Red 2 Were profitable inferior bought from the Huntsman Chemical Company. The ready for dyeing (RFD) fabrics, dyestuffs (Reactive Red 2), basic chemicals and auxiliaries (Urea, Exhaustion agent, Soaping agent, Non Ionic Detergent, LUTON 500, Non Ionic Detergent, LUTON 500, Sodium Hydroxide (NaOH), Sodium Hydrogen Carbonate (NaHCO₃), (Sodium Carbonate(Na₂CO₃), Sodium Perborate Tetrahydrate (NaBo₃,4H₂O) Sodium Perborate Tetrahydrate (NaBo₃,4H₂O), etc. received from the reputed chemical company. In this experiment many more machineries were also used such as YALIRUO, Sample Dyeing Machine, HUIBAO Washing Machine, High Temperature drying machine, Spectrophotometer (Cary Series UV- Vis Spectrophotometer).

2.1 Fabric Preparation:

Plain woven fabric (100% Cotton) scoured and bleached samples were collected from fabric roll of the store house of lab. Average sample weight 8 gm. To inspect the fabric cleanliness and to check the Crease mark, Hole mark, Patta, GSM variation etc faults were checked. Cut fabric sample size from the roll was A4 size. For testing Single Factor 46 (Forty Six) samples and for Taguchi experiment 18 (eighteen) samples were taken and again after dyeing dyed weight were taken to uniform pick up%. For all the experimental design (Single Factor and Taguchi) pick up rate was ensured at 80%. Maximum tolerance level regarding the after weight of the fabric was $\pm 5\%$. For evaluating pick up% following formula was used. Thus, the fabric was prepared for the suitable next process like reactive dyeing which is shown below in equation 1.

$$\text{Pick-up rate \%} = \frac{\text{Dyed fabric weight} - \text{Grey fabric weight}}{\text{Dyed fabric weight}} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

2.2 Experimental Equipment

Scissors, Beakers, Dropper, Petridis, Glass rods, Electrical balances, Safety glass, Mask, Apron, Hand gloves, Small dryer machine, stapler, small tyre ball, multi fabric, grey scale etc. were additional equipment's for this experiment which is shown in Fig 2.

Figure 2: Structures of Red 2

2.3 Dyeing method Two dip two-pad process

Cotton plain woven RFD sample was sunk into a Reactive Red 2 solution and passed through the padding machine roller. Then first padded sample again put in Reactive Red 2 and passed through the padding

machine roller. This process is called two-dip two pad process.

2.4 Dyeing of cotton fabric by reactive dyes

Cotton plain woven fabrics dyed with the Reactive Red 2. A4 size fabric sample was taken (total samples 46).

Dyeing Recipe of Cotton Fabrics, which are stated below in Table 1.

Table 1: Dyeing formula of cotton fabrics

Dye mass (o.m.f)	2% (Variable)
Urea	30 gm/L
Temperature	95 °C (Variable)
Time	2 min(Variable)
Liquor ratio	1:20

Concentration of Na_2CO_3 , NaOH and NaHCO_3 according to PH value which are stated below in Table 2.

$\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3=0.1\text{M}=10.6 \text{ gm/L}$, $\text{NaOH}=0.1\text{M}=4 \text{ gm/L}$, $\text{NaHCO}_3=8.4 \text{ gm/L}$,

Table.2: Concentration of Na_2CO_3 , NaOH and NaHCO_3 according to PH Chart

Na_2CO_3 (ml)	NaHCO_3 (ml)	NaOH (ml)	P^{H}
5	95	N/A	9.03
60	40	N/A	10.02
90	10	N/A	11.09
90	N/A	10	12.01

2.5 Reactive Dyeing process

Bleached fabric and reactive dyestuff (Reactive Red 2) put together in small dyeing bath containing alkali like ($\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3/\text{NaHCO}_3/\text{NaOH}$) according to P^{H} requirement. After 10 minutes Urea was used as an exhausting agent. Again, the machine runs for 10 min and the temperature was increased up to 95°C . When the dye batch reached the temperature at 95°C then Sodium carbonate (Na_2CO_3) was mixed for fixation, run the dye bath at 95°C for 30 min. After that, the temperature was fallen on to 30°C . Finally, the dye bath was dropped and carried on the after-treatment process which is stated below in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Reactive dyeing curve of the cotton fabric

2.6 Washing Process of cotton knitted dyed fabric

To remove the regular impurities, residual auxiliaries, etc and for better color fastness properties. At first complete elimination of salts and alkali is required to perform by rinsing and then it needs soap wash to

confirm the complete recovery from unfixed dyes. Finally, the dyed sample was dried at 75-80°C. Wash recipe of cotton woven dyed sample, which is stated below in Table 3.

Table 3: Wash recipe of cotton woven dyed fabrics

Detergent	2gm/L
M: L	1:50
Temperature	95°C
Time	15 min

2.7 Single Factor Design

This is the elementary step of Taguchi design experiment. Here four level of control factors were selected i.e. Dyeing Concentration, drying temperature, drying time and PH. According to this design keeping three factors constant one factor is made variable. Based on the best color strength value of K/S one best variable factor is selected. For this particular design below stated design was followed. Find out Best P^H value which is given below in Table 4:

Table 4: Variable P^H

Dyeing concentration %	Drying temp (°C).	Drying time (min)	Variable P ^H	Best P ^H
10 gm/L	60°C	2min	8	9 based on K/S value
			9	
			10	
			11	
			12	

From the above Table 4 we found best P^H 9, changeable drying temperature (°C) which is shown below in Table 5.

Table.5: Changeable drying temperature

Dyeing concentration gm/L	P ^H	Drying time (min)	Variable drying temp. (°C)	Best drying temperature (°C)
10 gm/L	9	2min	30°C	60 °C based on K/S value
			40°C	
			50°C	
			60°C	
			70°C	
			80°C	
			90°	

From the above Table 5 we found best drying temperature at 60°C, different dyeing concentration which is shown below in Table 6.

Table 6: different dyeing concentration (gm/L)

Dyeing concentration gm/L	pH	Drying time (min)	Best drying temp. (°C)	Best dyeing concentration %
5gm/L	9	2min	60°C	10 gm/L based on K/S value
10 gm/L				
15 gm/L				
20 gm/L				
25 gm/L				
30 gm/L				

From the above Table 6 we found best dyeing concentration 10gm/L, different drying time which is shown below in Table 7.

Table 7: Different drying time

Dyeing concentration gm/L	pH	Drying time (min)	Best drying temp (°C)	Best drying time (min)
10 gm/L	9	1min	60°C	2min based on K/S value
		1.5 min		
		2 min		
		2.5 min		
		3min		

From the above Table 7 we found best dyeing drying time 2 min, finally we got four factors optimized condition which is shown below in Table 8.

Table 8: Suitable condition

Parameters	Best condition
Dyeing concentration	10 gm/L
pH	9
Drying temp	60°C
Drying time	2 min

2.8 Taguchi Method

Taguchi method was developed by Prof. Taguchi in 1950 emphasizing efficient utilization of engineering approach rather than advanced statistical scheme. A basic configuration of Taguchi tactic for successful optimization comprises six main steps such as -i) Identification of control factors and their level on the performance characteristics, ii) Set up the suitable Experimental Design, iii) Conducting experiments, iv) Analysis of experimental data, v) ANOVA, vi) Confirmation Experiment Engin et al; Mavruz & Ogulata,; Zeydan,) (10). The key objective of Taguchi methodology for optimization is to design optimum setting of process control parameters for maintaining the variance at a minimum level in the response, even in the existence of noise inputs(11). Taguchi defines the S/N ratio (η) as a performance criterion or quality index and expressed in decibels (dB). The higher S/N ratio represents the better product quality.

3. Result & discussion

To estimate dyeing performance, the color strength (K/S) and CIELAB of the cotton plain woven dyed samples were dignified using a Data color 400 spectro-photometer through illuminant D65 and 100 observer(12). The K/S value is intended by the Kubelka–Munk calculation, $K/S = (1 - R)^2 / 2R$, where R is the reflectance, K is the immersion quantity, and S is the sprinkle coefficient(13). The color variation is expressed as ΔE^* and is designed by Equation 2.

$$\Delta E^* = \sqrt{(\Delta L^*)^2 + (\Delta a^*)^2 + (\Delta b^*)^2} \quad (2)$$

Where ΔE^* is the CIELAB hue variance amongst batch then standard. Now ΔL^* , Δa^* , Δb^* and hence ΔE^* remain in proportionate parts. ΔL^* signifies the difference among lightness (where $L^* = 100$) then darkness (where $L^* = 0$), Δa^* the difference between red (+a*) and green (-a*) and Δb^* the difference between yellow (+b*) and blue (-b*). For the study, the amount of levelness was defined according to ΔE . All dignified samples indicated a maximum immersion wavelength value (λ_{max}) at 444 nm. The ΔE value is also an essential parameter in the dyeing procedure, which can indicate the amount of levelness of dyed fabric which is stated below in Table 9.

Table 9: Taghuchi Method for Reactive Red 2 based on color strength, mean, S/N and Predicted Noise Ratio.

STD	RUN	PH	Drying Temp(°C)	Dyeing Concentration (gm/L)	Drying Time(min)	K/S value	Mean	Signal Noise Ratio	Predicted-Noise Ratio using equation
1	1	8	50	5	1	0.404456529	40	32.0412	32.0412
2	2	8	60	10	2	0.316337536	32	30.1030	30.1030
3	3	9	60	15	1	0.584003759	36	31.1261	31.1261
4	4	9	70	5	2	0.746899855	67	36.5215	36.5215
5	5	8	70	15	3	0.364895622	58	35.2686	35.2686
6	6	10	60	5	3	0.863142571	75	37.5012	37.5012
7	7	10	50	15	2	0.785637973	79	37.9525	37.9525
8	8	9	50	10	3	0.671084353	86	38.6900	38.6900
9	9	10	70	10	1	0.86105983	86	38.6900	38.6900

From the above table 9 we got the four factors and three Levels which are shown below in Table 10.

Table.10: Factors and Level controllable system

Factors	Level			Code	Unit
	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3		
PH	8	9	10	A	N/A
Drying Temp. (°C)	50	60	70	B	°C
Dyeing Concentration (gm/L)	5	10	15	C	gm/L
Drying Time (min)	1	2	3	D	Min

3.1 Taguchi Analysis:

K/S versus PH, Drying Temp, Dyeing Concentration and Drying Time and response for mean which is stated below in Table 11 and Table 12 and Main effects plot for Signal to Noise ratio & Mean and which is shown below in Figure 4 and Figure 5.

Table.11: Signal to Noise Ratio (Larger is better)

Level	PH	Drying temp (°C)	Dyeing concentration (gm/L)	Drying time (min)
1	31.09	35.51	36.08	35.33
2	36.43	34.69	35.10	35.19
3	38.44	35.77	34.78	35.45
Delta	7.35	1.09	1.30	0.26
Rank	1	3	2	4
Optimum	A ₃	B ₃	C ₁	D ₃

Table 12: Response for Means

Level	PH	Drying temp (°C)	Dyeing concentration (gm/L)	Drying time (min)
1	36.00	62.00	67.00	61.33
2	66.67	58.67	61.67	62.00
3	83.67	65.67	57.67	63.00
Delta	47.67	7.00	9.33	1.67
Rank	1	3	2	4
Optimum	A ₃	B ₃	C ₁	D ₃

Figure.4: Main effects plot for SN ratio

Figure.5: Main effects plot for Mean

3.2 Analysis of Optimum Conditions

The optimal dyeing process parameters and their corresponding level values obtained are A₃, B₃, C₁, D₃ which indicate PH 10, drying temperature 70 °C, dyeing concentration 5 gm/L and drying time 3 minutes.

4. Conclusion

In the present study, Taguchi model has been developed for optimization of the dyeing process and predicting the fabric CS dyed with Reactive red 2 dye. The Taguchi model was built by taking dye concentration, dyeing time, drying temperature and PH as input variables and fabric K/S value as response variable. From the Taguchi design of optimization the optimal parameters in the dyeing process were found to be PH 10, dye concentration 5 gm/L, drying time 3 min and drying temperature 70 °C. It was observed from the ANOVA that dye PH is the significant factor (p-value < 0.5) at 95% confidence level. Further, the percentages contribution (PF) of different factors toward the K/S value are shown as succeeding array from Pareto Chart: PH (A) > Dyeing concentration (C) > Drying Temperature (B) > Drying Time (D). The proposed Taguchi model presents a nice approach about the interaction between the dyeing process parameters and their effects on the K/S value. It has been found that PH has the greatest and main effects on the K/S than other dyeing conditions. The Taguchi model derived in this research has been verified via confirmation experiment and unseen experimental data. It is observed that the predicted S/N ratio 38.45 at the optimum conditions is smaller than confirmation experimental S/N ratio. In addition, the confirmation experimental S/N ratio 38.7 under optimal conditions is found to be good agreement with the predicted S/N ratio 38.45

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